

GRAMMAR CATEGORIES AND VOCABULARY FORM OF ADJECTIVES IN LATIN LANGUAGE

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Abstract: This abstract tells about the adjectives and the groups of adjectives in Latin and some vocabulary and categories of the adjectives. We also get to know about adjective-noun agreement and adjective declensions of some Latin words.

Key words: declension, gender, adjective, form, categories, expression, topic, abbreviation, quantity.

Introduction

An adjective is a word that modifies a noun or a pronoun. Adjectives give us information about qualities and quantities. Here are few examples of adjectives in English language like: big, tall, red, pretty, ancient, happy etc... Latin adjectives work very much like English adjectives.

But since Latin language nouns have gender, number, and case, Latin adjectives also have these three properties. The number one rule of Latin adjectives is that they must agree with their nouns in gender number and case of the noun. The coordination of the adjectives with their nouns is called as agreement. And when they say that that the adjective agrees with its noun. We mean that it's gender number and case match the gender number and the case of noun. Further down in this post, we will explore adjective-noun agreement in the detail. But for now, just make to understand the basic topic and principles.

So here's the thing, if we are familiar with noun declensions, then you know that each noun has different form of based on the case and number.

Each adjective , on the other hand can have three genders. This is logical necessity as since adjectives have to be able to modify nouns of the every gender. What this means is that adjectives can have double or triple the number of endings as nouns. But before we get to know, Here are some good ways that adjectives can be adopted by us as the same endings as nouns. Now that we know some basic facts it's time know

some different types of Latin adjectives: there are 2 types- 1st and 2nd declension adjectives.

The first class of Latin adjectives is 1st and 2nd declension adjectives. How can adjectives be both first and second declension as simple. The adjectives are 1st declension in the feminine and 2nd declension in the masculine and neuter. This makes sense if you consider how the nouns of gender used. 1st declension nouns made usually feminine. 2nd declension in -us are masculine and while 2nd declension nouns ending in -um are neuter.

Dictionaries and textbooks conventionally list the masculine and feminine and neuter nominative singular forms of 1st and 2nd declension adjectives. These forms end in -us, -a, and -um respectively. Here are some examples:

-magnus, magna, magnum: large, great

-bonus, bona, bonum - good

-albums, alba, album-white

As we can see, adjectives often appear in short hand: as the feminine and neuter nominative singulars are abbreviated to -a and -um. 1st and 2nd declension adjectives are declined exactly like nouns of the 1st and 2nd declension. The second main class of adjectives is 3rd declension adjective. Since the 3rd declension noun can be masculine feminine and neuter there are 3rd declension endings for every gender. Most 3rd declension adjectives have two sets of endings: the masculine feminine nominative singular and neuter nominative singular.

For standard 3rd declension adjectives, the masculine and feminine ends in -is and the neuter ends in -e. These two forms appear in dictionary and textbook entries.

Conclusion

The adjectives discussed in this exploration steeped in the linguistic traditions of Latin. Contribute distinctive fair to the English language. The conclusion undergoes the versatility of these adjectives. Emphasize the role in providing clarity, decisiveness and sense of finality to expressions and descriptions.

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